

Toward a Universal GPU Instruction Set Architecture: A Cross-Vendor Analysis of Hardware-Invariant Computational Primitives in Parallel Processors

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Abstract— We present the first systematic cross-vendor analysis of GPU instruction set architectures spanning all four major GPU vendors: NVIDIA (PTX ISA v1.0 through v9.2, Fermi through Blackwell), AMD (RDNA 1 to 4 and CDNA 1 to 4), Intel (Gen11, Xe-LP, Xe-HPG, Xe-HPC), and Apple (G13, reverse-engineered). Drawing on official ISA reference manuals, architecture whitepapers, patent filings, and community reverse-engineering efforts totaling over 5,000 pages of primary sources across 16 distinct microarchitectures, we identify ten hardware-invariant computational primitives that appear across all four architectures, six parameterizable dialects where vendors implement identical concepts with different parameters, and six true architectural divergences representing fundamental design disagreements. Based on this analysis, we propose an abstract execution model for a vendor-neutral GPU ISA grounded in the physical constraints of parallel computation. We argue that the observed convergence is driven by thermodynamic and information-theoretic necessity: the cost of instruction fetch relative to arithmetic, the memory-compute bandwidth gap, and the area-latency tradeoff in on-chip storage, rather than by convention. We validate our model with benchmark results on NVIDIA T4 and Apple M1 hardware, the two most architecturally distant platforms in our study. On five of six benchmark-platform pairs, the abstract model matches or exceeds native vendor-optimized performance. The single outlier (parallel reduction on NVIDIA, 62.5% of native) reveals that intra-wave shuffle must be a mandatory primitive, a finding that refines our proposed model.

1 INTRODUCTION

The GPU computing ecosystem is dominated by a single proprietary software stack. NVIDIA’s CUDA platform, comprising the PTX virtual ISA, the NVCC compiler, and the cuDNN/cuBLAS library ecosystem, has become the de facto standard for GPU-accelerated computation in machine learning, scientific computing, and high-performance data processing. This dominance persists not because of hardware superiority alone but because of software lock-in: code written for CUDA cannot execute on AMD, Intel, or Apple GPUs without significant rewriting effort.

Several portable GPU programming interfaces exist. OpenCL [19], Vulkan Compute, and SYCL provide cross-vendor APIs. SPIR-V [20] provides a portable intermediate representation. However, these systems operate at the API and IR level, deliberately abstracting away the hardware exe-

cution model. They do not define what a GPU *is* at the architectural level; they define a contract for talking to one. The consequence is that performance-critical code must still be tuned per vendor, and portable interfaces often achieve only 50 to 80% of native performance [23].

We observe that a different approach is possible. The ARM instruction set architecture did not succeed by providing a portable API to heterogeneous CPU hardware. It succeeded by defining a common execution model precise enough that multiple vendors could implement it efficiently in silicon while maintaining binary compatibility. No equivalent exists for GPU computation.

In this paper, we ask: *is such an architecture possible for GPUs?* Specifically:

What are the fundamental, hardware-invariant computational primitives that all GPU architectures share, and can they be formalized into a universal instruction set architecture?

Our hypothesis is that the observed convergence in GPU architecture across vendors is not coincidental but is driven by computational necessity. If correct, the shared primitives can be identified empirically, formalized precisely, and specified as a vendor-neutral ISA that any manufacturer could implement without sacrificing performance.

1.1 Contributions

1. The first comprehensive cross-vendor GPU ISA analysis spanning NVIDIA, AMD, Intel, and Apple across 16 microarchitectures and 15+ years of evolution.
2. Identification of ten hardware-invariant primitives with a physical-constraint argument for their necessity.
3. A taxonomy of six parameterizable dialects and six true divergences.
4. An abstract execution model following the *thin abstraction principle*.
5. Preliminary experimental validation on NVIDIA (T4) and Apple (M-series) hardware.

1.2 Scope and Limitations

Our analysis covers GPU architectures for general-purpose computation. We exclude NPUs, DSPs, and FPGAs. Apple GPU data relies on reverse-engineered sources with flagged confidence levels. Graphics pipeline primitives are out of scope.

2 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

2.1 GPU Architecture Landscape

Modern GPUs share a high-level organization: an array of compute units containing SIMD-capable pipelines, on-chip register files, and local scratchpad memory, connected through a cache hierarchy to high-bandwidth off-chip memory. However, ISA-level abstractions differ significantly. NVIDIA’s PTX [1] defines a virtual ISA with per-thread scalar semantics. AMD publishes native ISA reference guides [6, 8] exposing hardware instruction encodings. Intel [11] exposes a SIMD-register ISA with message-passing interfaces. Apple publishes no ISA documentation; community efforts [14, 15] provide partial coverage.

2.2 Portability Approaches

API-level portability. OpenCL [19] provides a portable execution model but does not specify hardware behavior below the API. SPIR-V [20] provides a portable binary IR consumed by vendor drivers. Vulkan Compute and SYCL offer additional abstraction layers. All require vendor-specific final compilation; none define the hardware execution model itself.

Compiler-level portability. Halide [21] separates algorithm from schedule for portable performance. MLIR [22] provides multi-level IR with progressive lowering. TVM [23] automates schedule search for specific targets. These compile to vendor backends; they do not define a universal hardware model.

Prior GPU architecture comparisons. Individual GPU architecture surveys exist [3, 9], but focus on single vendors. To our knowledge, no prior work has performed a systematic cross-vendor ISA-level analysis across all four major GPU vendors with the goal of identifying hardware-invariant primitives.

2.3 The ARM ISA Analogy

The ARM ISA, first defined in 1985, provides our closest analogy. ARM defines an ISA that multiple vendors implement with radically different microarchitectures while maintaining binary compatibility. The ISA contract is precise enough to constrain implementations and thin enough to permit microarchitectural innovation. We argue GPU architecture has converged sufficiently for an equivalent.

Table 1: Notation

Symbol	Definition
W	Wave width (threads per lockstep group)
R	Maximum registers per thread
S	Local memory (scratchpad) size in bytes
F	Register file size per core in bytes
O	Occupancy (resident waves per core)
w	Register width in bytes (typically 4)

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Notation

Table 1 defines symbols used throughout.

3.2 Data Sources

Our analysis draws on over 5,000 pages of primary sources: **NVIDIA:** PTX ISA v1.0 [2], v8.7, v9.2 [1]; Volta whitepaper [3]; Blackwell microbenchmarks [4]; three patents [24–26].

AMD: RDNA 1 to 4 [5, 6] and CDNA 1 to 4 [7, 8] ISA guides (~4,800 pages); CDNA 2 [9] and CDNA 3 [10] whitepapers.

Intel: Gen11 [13], Xe-HPG [11], OneAPI guide [12], Hot Chips 2020.

Apple: G13 reference [14], M1 GPU analysis [15, 16], Metal Benchmarks [17], AMX patent [18].

3.3 Analytical Framework

For each vendor, we extracted details along eight dimensions: execution model, SIMD structure, register file, memory hierarchy, instruction categories, synchronization, scheduling, and design choices. Per-vendor longitudinal synthesis identified *constants*, *evolution*, and *unique features*. Cross-vendor synthesis classified each dimension as *invariant*, *parameterizable*, or *divergent*.

4 CROSS-VENDOR ANALYSIS

4.1 Hardware-Invariant Primitives

We identify ten primitives present in all four architectures (Table 2). We argue these are computational necessities that emerged independently across vendors over 15 years.

4.1.1 Physical Rationale

The invariants trace to physical constraints:

Lockstep groups exist because instruction fetch costs 10 to 100× more energy than single-lane arithmetic at modern nodes. Amortizing one fetch across W lanes is necessary for energy efficiency.

Mask-based divergence is the only mechanism compatible with lockstep execution that preserves correctness without branch prediction.

Table 2: Ten Hardware-Invariant Primitives Across All Four GPU Vendors

Invariant	NVIDIA	AMD	Intel	Apple
1. Lockstep thread group	Warp (32)	Wavefront (32/64)	Sub-group (8 to 16)	SIMD-group (32)
2. Mask-based divergence	Per-thread PC + predicates	EXEC register (compiler)	Predicated SIMD (compiler)	Stack in r0l (hardware)
3. Register-occupancy tradeoff	255 regs from 256 KB/SM	256 VGPRs per wave	128 GRF per thread	128 GPRs from 208 KB
4. Managed scratchpad	Shared memory (228 KB)	LDS (64 to 160 KB)	SLM (64 to 512 KB)	Threadgroup mem (~60 KB)
5. Zero-cost context switch	All warp state resident	All wave state resident	IMT, 7 to 8 threads/EU	24 SIMD-groups resident
6. Hierarchical memory	Reg, Shmem, L1, L2, DRAM	Reg, LDS, L0/1/2, VRAM	Reg, SLM, L1/2, DRAM	Reg, TG, L1/2/3, DRAM
7. Atomic RMW	atom/red (all scopes)	DS/buffer/global atomics	SEND atomics	32-bit device atomics
8. Workgroup barrier	bar.sync (16 named)	S_BARRIER	Barrier (WG scope)	threadgroup_barrier
9. Identity registers	%tid, %ctaid, %laneid	VGPR0 (thread_id)	sr0 (local_id)	thread_position
10. Async memory + sync	cp.async / mbarrier	S_WAITCNT counters	SEND + scoreboard	device_load + wait

Table 3: Parameterizable Dialects

Parameter	NV	AMD	Intel	Apple
Wave width W	32	32/64	8 to 16	32
Max regs R	255	256	128/256	128
Scratchpad S	228K	128K	512K	~60K
Max workgroup	1024	1024	1024	1024
Named barriers	16	1 to 32	1	1
Native FP64	Yes	Varies	HPC	No

The **register-occupancy tradeoff** follows from fixed SRAM area:

$$O = \left\lceil \frac{F}{R \times W \times w} \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

Programmer-managed scratchpad persists because parallel access patterns require explicit data placement that caches cannot predict.

Zero-cost switching is cheaper than speculation because memory latency (100 to 800 cycles) dominates, and SRAM for thread state costs less area than branch predictors.

Workgroup-scope barriers (not global) exist because global barriers would require all workgroups to be simultaneously resident.

4.2 Parameterizable Dialects

Six dimensions implement identical concepts with vendor-specific parameters (Table 3). In our model, these become queryable constants.

4.3 True Architectural Divergences

Six areas exhibit fundamentally incompatible approaches (Table 4), defining abstraction boundaries.

Table 4: True Architectural Divergences and Proposed Resolutions

Area	Vendor Approaches	Our Resolution
Divergence	NV: HW per-thread PC; AMD: compiler EXEC; Intel: predication; Apple: HW stack	Structured control flow
Scalar/ vector	AMD: SALU/VALU split; others: unified	Unified; compiler hoists
Hierarchy	NV: 4 levels; others: 3	3 mandatory + optional
Matrix	Incompatible tiles/flows	Opaque + queryable
Memory order	Axiomatic / counter / scoreboard / async	Scoped acq/rel
Fixed-fn	SEND / opcodes / loads	Opaque operations

5 THE PROPOSED ABSTRACT EXECUTION MODEL

We define an execution model following the *thin abstraction principle*: precise enough to compile against, thin enough for any vendor to implement efficiently. Figure 1 shows the thread hierarchy; Figure 2 shows the memory model.

5.1 Core Specification

Compute Unit. One or more Cores, each with resident Waves (width W), R private 32-bit registers per thread, S bytes of scratchpad. Hardware scheduler switches Waves at zero cost.

Registers. Per-thread, 32-bit scalar, 16-bit addressable halves. No vector types; SIMD implicit through Wave. Occupancy: Eq. 1.

Figure 1: Thread hierarchy: three mandatory levels plus optional cluster (dashed).

Figure 2: Memory hierarchy with scoped ordering semantics. Caches are transparent to the ISA.

Memory. Registers (private) \rightarrow scratchpad (workgroup, explicit) \rightarrow device memory (global, cached, async). Scoped acquire/release: wave, workgroup, device, system.

Instructions. Integer/FP arithmetic (F16/F32 required; F64/BF16 optional), conversion, comparison, scratchpad/device load/store, atomic RMW, shuffle, barrier, fence. Optional: matrix MMA with queryable tiles.

Control Flow. Structured: `if/else/endif`, `loop/break/endloop`, `call/return`. Divergence mechanism hidden.

Scheduling. Hardware selects ready Waves. No pipeline latencies exposed. Compiler manages registers and optional hints.

6 MAPPING ANALYSIS

Figure 3 illustrates the mapping from abstract model to vendor architectures.

NVIDIA. Waves \rightarrow warps ($W=32$). Registers \rightarrow PTX registers. Scratchpad \rightarrow shared memory. Control flow \rightarrow predicated divergence. Memory model maps losslessly to PTX scoped semantics.

AMD. Waves \rightarrow wavefronts ($W=32/64$). Registers \rightarrow VGPRs. Scratchpad \rightarrow LDS. Control flow \rightarrow EXEC mask. Memory \rightarrow S_WAITCNT. Backend hoists uniform ops to SALU.

Intel. Waves \rightarrow sub-groups ($W \in \{8, 16\}$). Registers \rightarrow GRF. Scratchpad \rightarrow SLM. Control flow \rightarrow predicated SIMD. Fixed-function via opaque ops over SEND.

Figure 3: Abstract model mapped to four vendor architectures. Every primitive has a direct, efficient native mapping.

Apple. Waves \rightarrow SIMD-groups ($W=32$). Registers \rightarrow GPRs. Scratchpad \rightarrow threadgroup memory. Control flow \rightarrow r01 stack. FP64/matrix: absent capabilities.

7 EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

We validate the model with three benchmark kernels on the two most architecturally distant platforms in our study: NVIDIA T4 (Turing, discrete GPU, GDDR6, Google Colab) and Apple M1 (unified memory, LPDDR4X, local).

7.1 Methodology

For each benchmark, we compare three implementations:

1. **Native:** Hand-written CUDA (NVIDIA) or Metal (Apple) using vendor-specific features: bank-conflict-free shared memory padding, `_shfl_down_sync` warp shuffles, `#pragma unroll`, per-warp histogram privatization (NVIDIA); `simd_shuffle_down`, `fma` intrinsics (Apple).
2. **Abstract:** Same algorithm, but restricted to only universal ISA primitives: flat scratchpad load/store, workgroup barriers, basic arithmetic, atomics. No vendor-specific intrinsics, no warp/SIMD-group shuffles, no bank-conflict padding, no compiler hints.
3. **Library (GEMM only):** cuBLAS on NVIDIA as an upper-bound reference for what a vendor-optimized implementation achieves at peak.

Parameters: GEMM with $N=4096$ (FP32), reduction with $N=2^{24}$, histogram with $N=2^{24}$ and 256 bins. Each measurement: median of 100 runs after 10 warmup iterations.

Important scope note: Our native and abstract implementations are structurally equivalent tiled kernels that differ only in which primitives they use. We are measuring the *cost of removing vendor-specific features from an equivalent implementation*, not claiming competitive performance with

Table 5: Performance: Abstract Model vs. Native (median of 100 runs). Bold indicates abstract $\geq 95\%$ of native.

Kernel	Platform	Native	Abs/Nat	Library
GEMM	NVIDIA T4	0.72 TF	126.1%	~8 TF
	Apple M1	1.22 TF	101.2%	n/a
Reduction	NVIDIA T4	280.1 GB/s	62.5%	n/a
	Apple M1	71.3 GB/s	97.8%	n/a
Histogram	NVIDIA T4	78.8 Kops	100.4%	n/a
	Apple M1	58.9 Kops	102.1%	n/a

vendor-optimized libraries. The cuBLAS comparison establishes the distance between our tiled implementations and peak library performance.

7.2 Results

7.3 Analysis

GEMM. On NVIDIA T4, both native and abstract implementations achieve 0.72 and 0.91 TFLOPS respectively, well below the T4’s ~8 TFLOPS cuBLAS peak. This is expected: our implementations are single-pass 32×32 tiled kernels without register blocking, double buffering, or multi-level tiling that production GEMM libraries employ. The relevant comparison is not absolute throughput but the *relative* cost of removing vendor features from an equivalent kernel. The abstract version is 26% faster because NVIDIA’s bank-conflict padding (`TILE+1`) wastes shared memory, while flat indexing gives `nvcc` a more favorable optimization path. On Apple M1, both versions achieve 1.22 TFLOPS with the abstract at 101.2%, indicating the Metal compiler optimizes both equivalently.

Reduction. The critical result. On NVIDIA T4, the abstract model achieves only 62.5% of native because the native version uses `_shfl_down_sync` for the final 32 elements, avoiding five barrier-synchronized shared memory round trips. On Apple M1, the same barrier-only abstract implementation achieves 97.8% because Apple’s memory subsystem and hardware scheduler tolerate the extra barriers with minimal overhead. This asymmetry reveals a precise architectural insight: **intra-wave shuffle is essential for NVIDIA but optional for Apple**, and therefore must be a mandatory primitive in the universal ISA to achieve portable performance.

Histogram. Essentially tied on both platforms (100.4% NVIDIA, 102.1% Apple). The native NVIDIA version uses per-warp privatized histograms to reduce shared-memory atomic contention, but on this workload the contention is insufficient for privatization to help. The abstract model’s single shared histogram performs equivalently.

Summary. Five of six configurations exceed our 80% viability threshold, with four exceeding 100%. The single outlier identifies a specific missing primitive (shuffle) rather than a fundamental flaw in the abstraction. With shuffle added to

the mandatory set, we expect all six configurations to exceed 95%.

7.4 Threats to Validity

We acknowledge several limitations of this evaluation:

Baseline strength. Our native implementations are hand-written tiled kernels, not production-optimized library code. The GEMM native baseline achieves ~9% of cuBLAS peak on NVIDIA. A stronger baseline (e.g., register-blocked, double-buffered tiling) would provide a more demanding test of the abstraction cost. We deliberately chose structurally equivalent implementations to isolate the effect of removing vendor-specific primitives, but this means our results represent a lower bound on the true abstraction cost for heavily optimized code.

Vendor coverage. We benchmark on two of four vendors. NVIDIA and Apple represent the most architecturally distant pair in our study (discrete vs. unified memory, hardware vs. stack-based divergence, different ISA philosophies), so the results provide meaningful coverage of the design space. AMD and Intel benchmarks are in progress and will be included in the extended version.

Workload diversity. Three kernels cover compute-bound (GEMM), bandwidth-bound (reduction), and atomic-bound (histogram) regimes. Irregular workloads (sparse computation, data-dependent control flow) and compound workloads (attention, FFT) remain as future work.

Apple confidence. Apple GPU architectural parameters are derived from reverse engineering. While performance measurements are direct, the interpretation of why the abstract model performs as it does on Apple relies on community-documented architectural details.

8 DISCUSSION

8.1 Why Now

Three factors make this timely. First, AI demand has made NVIDIA’s software dominance a single point of failure for global compute infrastructure. Second, geopolitical export controls on advanced semiconductors have made sovereign AI compute a national priority for multiple countries, creating demand for vendor-neutral software. Third, the architectural convergence documented here, spanning four independent vendors over 15 years, has reached sufficient maturity for the invariant primitives to be identified with confidence.

8.2 The Thin Abstraction Principle

The central principle is *thinness*: define what hardware must do, not how. We do not prescribe W ; we query it. We do not expose divergence; we define structured control flow. We do not specify caches; we define scopes. We do not dictate

matrix tiles; we query them. Each decision trades compile-time certainty for runtime flexibility, enabling one ISA to span hardware from mobile GPUs to datacenter accelerators.

Our experimental results validate this principle empirically. The cases where the abstract model *exceeds* native performance (GEMM on NVIDIA, histogram on Apple) demonstrate that vendor-specific “optimizations” can be counterproductive, because they encode assumptions about the hardware that may not hold across configurations. A thin abstraction avoids encoding such assumptions, allowing the compiler and hardware to find their own optimal path.

8.3 The Shuffle Insight

The reduction benchmark reveals that intra-wave shuffle occupies a unique position in the primitive hierarchy. Unlike barriers (which all vendors implement with similar overhead) or atomics (which scale similarly across vendors), shuffle performance is highly sensitive to the underlying hardware’s latency tolerance for shared memory accesses. On NVIDIA, where the warp scheduler aggressively pipelines warp-level operations, replacing shuffle with barrier-mediated shared memory access incurs a 37.5% penalty. On Apple, where the hardware scheduler has $8\times$ more SIMD-groups than needed to hide ALU latency, the same replacement costs only 2.2%.

This finding refines our model: the eleven mandatory primitives are the original ten invariants plus intra-wave shuffle. We note that all four vendors already implement shuffle in hardware (`_shfl` on NVIDIA, `DPP/ds.permute` on AMD, sub-group shuffle on Intel, `simd.shuffle` on Apple), so adding it to the mandatory set imposes no implementation burden.

8.4 Relationship to Existing Standards

Our model complements existing standards. SPIR-V could distribute programs targeting our ISA. OpenCL and Vulkan could serve as host APIs. The distinction: existing standards specify how to *talk to* a GPU; we specify what a GPU *is*.

8.5 Limitations and Future Work

Beyond the threats to validity discussed above, several items remain as future work. The formal ISA specification, including instruction encoding and binary format, is under active development and will be released as a companion technical report. AMD (RDNA/CDNA) and Intel (Xe) benchmarks are in progress using cloud GPU instances. Additional benchmarks targeting irregular workloads, compound ML operations (attention, layer normalization), and memory-divergent access patterns are planned. Finally, a prototype compiler from the universal ISA to vendor-native backends will provide the definitive test of whether the abstraction can be automated rather than hand-translated.

9 CONCLUSION

We have presented the first systematic cross-vendor GPU ISA analysis across all four major vendors and 16 microarchitectures. Ten hardware-invariant primitives emerge from the physical constraints of parallel computation. Our abstract execution model, following the thin abstraction principle, maps efficiently to all four architectures.

The convergence is not coincidence. Lockstep groups, masked divergence, register-occupancy tradeoffs, managed scratchpads, zero-cost switching, hierarchical memory, work-group barriers, and atomics reflect what a GPU *is*, independent of who built it. Our benchmark results on NVIDIA T4 and Apple M1 demonstrate that on five of six configurations, restricting to universal primitives matches or exceeds native performance. The single outlier identifies intra-wave shuffle as a mandatory primitive, refining rather than refuting the model. This opens the path to a vendor-neutral GPU ISA: the ARM of GPU computation.

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